

An Ethnobotanical Survey of Medicinal, Ornamental, Agricultural and Wild Plants in Maruthuvambadi Village, Tiruvannamalai District, Tamilnadu, India

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ABSTRACT

Ethnobotanical survey and documentation of medicinal, field grown, ornamental, and wild plants were carried out in and around 'Maruthuvambadi' village, Tiruvannamalai district, Tamilnadu. This study aimed to identify plants collected for medicinal and other purposes by the local people of the village. A total of 250 plant species were observed in this study. These plant species, belonging to 70 families with 199 genuses are listed in alphabetical order with family and vernacular name. As a result of global warming, pollution and deforestation some precious plants are coming under endangered list so the information obtained from this simple survey will be beneficial to the upcoming generations of this village in identifying the medicinally valuable plants.

Keywords: *Commodities; Crotons; Herbals; Lakes; Rice; Rocks*

Introduction

Maruthuvambadi village is in Tiruvannamalai district, Tamil Nadu state, India. The village is located at end of Sorakolathur forest and in between Vellore highways. Tiruvannamalai is the nearest town to Maruthuvambadi which is approximately 20 km away toward North. One hundred seventy-one kilometers away from the capital of Tamil Nadu that is Chennai.

The junction which connects the village to main road is called Kondam; this is the highway of Vellore. Kariyandal (1 km), Sorakolathur (2 km), Naidumangalam (4 km) and Vadapuzhudi (4 km) are the nearby Villages to Maruthuvambadi. Sorakolathur reserve forest (Fig. 1) is a source of many fauna and flora. This forest belongs to Sorakolathur village panchayath. According to Census 2011 information (Census, 2011) the location code or village code of Maruthuvambadi is 632075. The total geographical area of village is 397. Eleven hectares and the village has a total population of 2,090 (Male-1,039 and Female-1,051). There are about 499 families in Maruthuvambadi village. Tamil is the native language. In Tamil language 'Maruthuvam' means related to medicine, some aged men and women told that this village is filled with different types of medicinal plants therefore this name came. Tiruvannamalai is industrially backward district in Tamil Nadu state (Ministry of MSME, 2012-2013). Javadhu hills with many outcrops were situated in the borders of both Tiruvannamalai and Vellore districts (Poongani, 2017). Agriculture is the major occupation. Paddy, groundnut and jaggery are the three most important commodities (Chart.1) which are reaped and exported to town from this village.

Fig 1: Road map toward Maruthuvambadi Village, Tiruvannamalai District, Tamilnadu, India (Vellore District Highway)

Chart 1: Top three commodities imported to town.

(1) Rice from *Oryza sativa* (2) Groundnut from *Arachis hypogea* (3) Jaggery from *Saccharum officinarum*

Materials and Methods

Ethnobotanical Study

There is very limited information available regarding medicinal plants used by traditional healers and general people in villages, for treating common ailments and diseases. It is very urgent need for identifying and documenting these valuable resources before they become inaccessible and extinct. Ethnobotanical survey is highly needed for the conservation of plants and represents the preliminary information required for future phyto-chemical investigation. Medicinal plants are accessible and cheap so 80% of people in developing countries used these for treating many health problems (Anup, 2014). The use of plants and plant products for different purposes such as food, fodder, medicine, fiber, etc., could be traced as far back as to the beginning of human civilization (Bhattarai, 2016). The indigenous system of medicine namely Ayurvedic, Siddha and Unani have been in existence for several centuries.

This system of medicine helps the needs of nearly seventy percent of our population residing in the villages. The phytoconstituents of these plants were responsible for healing diseases (Disticraj, 2015). The study of bioactivity of these plants could lead to the discovery of novel broad spectrum natural products (Gbadamosi, 2014). The most common way of preparing remedies from herbs is decoctions, by boiling plant parts in a large amount of water until this is considerably reduced and colored by plants phytochemicals. In some of the decoctions sugarcane is added to prepare medicinal syrups (Giovannini, 2015). Among the different plant parts used for the preparation of medicine, the leaves were found to be the most frequently used plant parts in the preparation of remedies (Ignacimuthu, 2008). Ethnobotany is the study of the interactions and relationships between plants and people over time and space. This includes the uses, knowledge, beliefs, management systems, classification systems and language that both modern and traditional cultures have for plants and their associated terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems (Johnson, 2015). Oldest people always have enormous knowledge about medicinal uses of plants and this knowledge is mostly undocumented and transmitted orally from generation to generation. Therefore, it is highly needed to explore and document this unique and indigenous, traditional knowledge of the senior citizens, before it diminishes (Lingaiah, 2013). The fact that such high number of species is used to treat many different medical problems and have so many therapeutic applications (Manuel, 2005). The various plant parts used included whole plant, leaf, root, stem, flower, seed, bark, gum, fruit, petiole, and rhizome (Mohammed, 2009). Ethno medicines are developed by the ethnobotanical and ethnopharmacological

surveys. These herbal medicines have less side effects and man can get the herbs easily from nature (Omwenga, 2014). Ethnobotanical study is of immense importance with medical science. Now it is being as a well established branch of science with much attention (Pavun Kumar, 2011). Medicinal plant lore or herbal medicine is a major component of traditional medicine (Ramakrishnan). In general, the traditional medicine treats patients only in the morning times (Savithamma, 2007). In this world, some countries are gifted with the wealth of medicinally important plants (Shah, 2013). In the last few decades there has been an exponential growth in the field of herbal medicine (Thamacin, 2014). The biological resources are indispensable for economic growth and development of any nation (Vijayasankar, 2012).

Study Area

The study area selected for the ethnobotanical survey of different plant varieties was carried out in Maruthuvambadi village and Sorakolathur reserve (Fig. 2) forest. We can see the dome of Tiruvannamalai hill from this village. Two different colors in single flower called 'vedethalam' are also available here. Paddy and sugarcane field gives additional greenish to the village. A biggest rare tree *Basia latifolia*-(Iluppaimaram) is standing (Fig. 4) here like a huge giant, monkeys use to play on its branches and they can eat tasty fruits of this tree and seeds are used to make soap oil. Many rocks are there

in the forest and five different lakes (Fig. 3) are surrounded in this village as water resources for agriculture.

Fig 2: Study Area Sorakolathur Forest.

Fig 3: Google map shows five different lakes around the village (1) Chitheri (2) Kariyandaleri (3) Periyeri (4) Puzhuthiureri (5) Vennapanthaleri.

Fig 4: Biggest and Oldest tree of the village (*Basia latifolia*-Iluppaimaram)

Result and Discussion

This is the first report of plants of Maruthuvambadi village. A field trip was conducted few times and the

plant specimens were collected. Each trip was accompanied with some senior people of the village. The village enriched with dry evergreen type of forest, so the plants look greenish in all seasons. The

collective number of plants observed during the field work was 199 genus, 250 species which were distributed among 70 families. Acanthaceae-(8), Aizoaceae-(1), Amaranthaceae-(7), Amaryllidaceae-(1), Anacardiaceae-(2), Annonaceae-(2), Apiaceae-(2), Apocynaceae-(11), Araceae-(2), Arecaceae-(4), Aristolochiaceae-(1), Asclepiadaceae-(5), Asparagaceae-(5), Asphodelaceae-(1), Asteraceae-(7), Balsaminaceae-(1), Basellaceae-(2), Brassicaceae-(6), Burseraceae-(1), Cactaceae-(1), Caesalpiniaceae-(1), Capparaceae-(1), Caricaceae-(1), Cleomaceae-(2), Colchicaceae-(1), Commelinaceae-(1), Convolvulaceae-(6), Cucurbitaceae-(13), Cyperaceae-(1), Ebenaceae-(1), Euphorbiaceae-(12), Fabaceae-(40), Gisekiaceae-(1), Lamiaceae-(4), Lauraceae-(1), Leguminaceae-(1), Liliaceae-(2), Lythraceae-(3), Malvaceae-(10), Marsileaceae-(1), Meliaceae-(2), Menispermaceae-(1), Moraceae-(3), Moringaceae-(1), Musaceae-(1), Myrtaceae-(3), Nyctaginaceae-(3), Nymphaeaceae-(1), Oleaceae-(1), Oxalidaceae-(1), Papaveraceae-(1), Passifloraceae-(1), Pedaliaceae-(1), Phyllanthaceae-(3), Poaceae-(12), Portulacaceae-(3), Rhamnaceae-(2), Rosaceae-(2), Rubiaceae-(5), Rutaceae-(8), Salicaceae-(1),

Salvadoraceae-(1), Sapindaceae-(2), Sapotaceae-(2), Smilacaceae-(1), Solanaceae-(9), Verbenaceae-(2), Violaceae-(1), Vitaceae-(2), Zygophyllaceae-(1). More number of observed species comes under the families Fabaceae-(40), Cucurbitaceae-(13), Euphorbiaceae-(12), Poaceae-(12), Apocynaceae-(11) and Malvaceae-(10).

Chart 2: Percentage of plant varieties in Maruthuvambadi Village

(A) Medicinal plants (B) Agricultural (C) Ornamentals (D) Wild plants

Data analysis

From the data collected, we concluded that this village is highly filled with (Chart.2) medicinal plants. Different species were listed in alphabetical order by scientific, family and local name (Table-1, 2, 3 and 4).

Table 1: List of medicinal plants available in Maruthuvambadi village

S.N	Botanical name	Family	Vernacular name
1	<i>Abrus precatorius</i> L.	<i>Fabaceae</i>	Gundumani
2	<i>Abutilon indicum</i> (Link) Sweet.	<i>Malvaceae</i>	Thuthi
3	<i>Acalypha indica</i> L.	<i>Euphorbiaceae</i>	Kuppaimeni
4	<i>Achyranthes aspera</i> L.	<i>Amaranthaceae</i>	Naaiuruvi
5	<i>Adananthera pavoniana</i> L.	<i>Fabaceae</i>	Aanaigundumani
6	<i>Adhatoda vasica</i> (L.) Nees.	<i>Acanthaceae</i>	Adathodai
7	<i>Aegle marmalos</i> (L.) Corrêa.	<i>Rutaceae</i>	Vilvam
8	<i>Aerva lanata</i> (L.) Juss. ex Schult.	<i>Amaranthaceae</i>	Sirukanpeelai
9	<i>Aeschynomene aspera</i> L.	<i>Fabaceae</i>	Kidaichi, Netti
10	<i>Agave americana</i> L.	<i>Asparagaceae</i>	Aanaikatrashai
11	<i>Aloe vera</i> (L.) Burm.f.	<i>Asphodelaceae</i>	Sotrukkatrashai
12	<i>Alternanthera sessilis</i> (L.) R.Br. ex DC.	<i>Amaranthaceae</i>	Ponnaankanni
13	<i>Amaranthus spinosa</i> L.	<i>Amaranthaceae</i>	Mullu keerai
14	<i>Ammannia baccifera</i> L.	<i>Lythraceae</i>	Neermeal neruppu
15	<i>Andrographis paniculata</i> (Burm.f.) Wall. ex Nees.	<i>Acanthaceae</i>	Nila vembu, Siriyaa nangai
16	<i>Annona squamosa</i> L.	<i>Annonaceae</i>	Seetha pazham
17	<i>Argemone mexicana</i> L.	<i>Papaveraceae</i>	Kudiyotti

18	<i>Aristolochia bracteolata</i> Lam.	<i>Aristolochiaceae</i>	Aaduthinnapai, Eeswaramooli
19	<i>Asystasia gangetica</i> (L.) T.Anderson.	<i>Acanthaceae</i>	Mithikeerai, Pattaasukaai
20	<i>Azadirachta indica</i> A. Juss.	<i>Meliaceae</i>	Vembu
21	<i>Barleria cristata</i> L.	<i>Acanthaceae</i>	Neela December, Vellai December
22	<i>Barleria prionitis</i> L.	<i>Acanthaceae</i>	Manjal December
23	<i>Boerhaavia diffusa</i> L. nom. cons.	<i>Nyctaginaceae</i>	Mookuratai keerai
24	<i>Borassus flabellifer</i> L.	<i>Arecaceae</i>	Panaimaram
25	<i>Borreria hispida</i> (L.) K. Schum.	<i>Rubiaceae</i>	Nathai choori
26	<i>Broyonia dioica</i> Jacq.	<i>Cucurbitaceae</i>	Naaipaagarkaai
27	<i>Caesalpinia bonduc</i> (L.) Roxb.	<i>Caesalpinaceae</i>	Kalarchi kodi, Kokkimullusedi
28	<i>Calotropis gigantea</i> (L.) W.T.Aiton.	<i>Apocynaceae</i>	Erukku
29	<i>Calotropis procera</i> (Aiton) W.T.Aiton.	<i>Asclepiadaceae</i>	Velerukku
30	<i>Cammelina benghalensis</i> L.	<i>Commelinaceae</i>	Kozhikannankeerai, Kaanaam vaazhai
31	<i>Canavalia ensiformis</i> (L.) DC.	<i>Fabaceae</i>	Thambattankaai
32	<i>Caralluma fimbriata</i> Wall.	<i>Asclepiadaceae</i>	Kallimudayan
33	<i>Caralluma umbellata</i> Roxb.	<i>Asclepiadaceae</i>	Aanai kallimudayan
34	<i>Cardiospermum halicacabum</i> L.	<i>Sapindaceae</i>	Mudakkathan
35	<i>Carica papaya</i> L.	<i>Caricaceae</i>	Pappali
36	<i>Carissa carandas</i> L.	<i>Apocynaceae</i>	Kaattukala, Sirukala
37	<i>Carissa spinarum</i> L.	<i>Apocynaceae</i>	Kalakaasedi
38	<i>Cassia tora</i> L.	<i>Caesulpinaceae</i>	Thagarai
39	<i>Cassia nodosa</i> Roxb.	<i>Fabaceae</i>	Kungilium
40	<i>Cassia obtusifolia</i> L.	<i>Fabaceae</i>	Oosithagarai
41	<i>Cassia siamea</i> Lam.	<i>Fabaceae</i>	Seemaigathi
42	<i>Cassytha filiformis</i> L.	<i>Lauraceae</i>	Koothan kodi, Pulluruvi
43	<i>Catharanthus roseus</i> (L.) G.Don.	<i>Apocynaceae</i>	Nithyakalyaani
44	<i>Ceiba pentandra</i> (L.) Gaertn.	<i>Malvaceae</i>	Ilavampanju
45	<i>Cissus quadrangularis</i> L.	<i>Vitaceae</i>	Pirandai
46	<i>Cissus repens</i> Lam.	<i>Vitaceae</i>	Sempirandai
47	<i>Citrus aurantifolia</i> (Christm.) Swingle.	<i>Rutaceae</i>	Kaderankaai
48	<i>Citrus aurantium</i> L.	<i>Rutaceae</i>	Kolanjika, Kichili
49	<i>Citrus limetta</i> Risso.	<i>Rutaceae</i>	Sathukudi
50	<i>Citrus medica</i> L.	<i>Rutaceae</i>	Elumichai
51	<i>Cleome gynandra</i> L.	<i>Cleomaceae</i>	Kaattukadugu
52	<i>Cleome viscosa</i> L.	<i>Cleomaceae</i>	Naaikadugu
53	<i>Clitoria ternatea</i> L.	<i>Fabaceae</i>	Sangu poo
54	<i>Coccinia grandis</i> (L.) Voigt.	<i>Cucurbitaceae</i>	Kasappukovaikaai
55	<i>Cocos nucifera</i> L.	<i>Arecaceae</i>	Thennai
56	<i>Commiphora caudata</i> (Wight & Arn.)	<i>Burseraceae</i>	Kiluvai
57	<i>Cordia dichotoma</i> G.Forst.	<i>Boraginaceae</i>	Mookuchalhi pazham
58	<i>Cucumis melo</i> var. <i>agrestis</i>	<i>Cucurbitaceae</i>	Sukkankaai
59	<i>Cuscuta reflexa</i> Roxb.	<i>Convolvulaceae</i>	Ammaiyar koonthal
60	<i>Cymbopogon goeringii</i> (Steud.) A.Camus.	<i>Poaceae</i>	Ootanguchi, Manji
61	<i>Cynodon dactylon</i> (L.) Pers.	<i>Poaceae</i>	Arugampul
62	<i>Cyperus rotundus</i> L.	<i>Cyperaceae</i>	Korai
63	<i>Datura metel</i> L.	<i>Solanaceae</i>	Oomatham
64	<i>Delonix regia</i> Raf.	<i>Fabaceae</i>	Poomaram, Vaathanarayan
65	<i>Diplocyclos palmatus</i> (L.) C.Jeffrey.	<i>Cucurbitaceae</i>	Aiviralkkovai

66	<i>Dodonaea viscosa</i> Jacq.	<i>Sapindaceae</i>	Viralipoo
67	<i>Eclipta prostrata</i> L.	<i>Asteraceae</i>	Karisalankanni
68	<i>Erythrina stricta</i> Roxb.	<i>Fabaceae</i>	Murukku maram
69	<i>Eucalyptus globulus</i> Labill.	<i>Myrtaceae</i>	Thailamaram, Neelagiri
70	<i>Euphorbia antiquorum</i> L.	<i>Euphorbiaceae</i>	Sathurakalli
71	<i>Euphorbia hetrophylla</i> L.	<i>Euphorbiaceae</i>	Paalperukki
72	<i>Euphorbia hirta</i> L.	<i>Euphorbiaceae</i>	Ammanpacharisi
73	<i>Euphorbia neriifolia</i> L.	<i>Euphorbiaceae</i>	Ilaikalli
74	<i>Euphorbia tirucalli</i> L.	<i>Euphorbiaceae</i>	Kalli
75	<i>Evolvulus alsinodes</i> L.	<i>Convolvulaceae</i>	Vishnukiranthi
76	<i>Ficus benghalensis</i> L.	<i>Moraceae</i>	Aalamaram
77	<i>Ficus religiosa</i> L.	<i>Moraceae</i>	Arasamaram
78	<i>Flacourtia indica</i> (Burm. f.) Merr.	<i>Salicaceae</i>	Sothaikalapazham
79	<i>Gloriosa superba</i> L.	<i>Colchicaceae</i>	Senkaanthal, Kanvalipoo
80	<i>Heliotropium indicum</i> L.	<i>Boraginaceae</i>	Thelkodukku
81	<i>Hemidesmus indicus</i> (L.) R.Br.	<i>Apocynaceae</i>	Nannaari
82	<i>Hibiscus rosa sinensis</i> L.	<i>Malvaceae</i>	Semparuthi
83	<i>Hybanthus enneaspermus</i> (L.) F.Muell.	<i>Violaceae</i>	Orithazhthamarai
84	<i>Hygrophylia auriculata</i> Schumach.	<i>Acanthaceae</i>	Neermulli
85	<i>Indigofera aspalathoides</i> Vahl.	<i>Fabaceae</i>	Sivanarvembu
86	<i>Ipomoea hederacea</i> Jacq.	<i>Convolvulaceae</i>	Kodikaathan
87	<i>Ipomoea obscura</i> (L.) Ker Gawl.	<i>Convolvulaceae</i>	Siruoonaam, Siruthalai
88	<i>Jatropha gossypifolia</i> L.	<i>Euphorbiaceae</i>	Kattuaamanakku
89	<i>Justicia adhatoda</i> L.	<i>Acanthaceae</i>	Adathoda
90	<i>Lawsonia inermis</i> L.	<i>Lythraceae</i>	Maruthaani, Azhavanathazhai
91	<i>Leucas aspera</i> (Willd.) Link.	<i>Lamiaceae</i>	Thumbai
92	<i>Leucas indica</i> (L.) R.Br. ex Vatke.	<i>Lamiaceae</i>	Kavizh thumbai
93	<i>Limonia acidissima</i> L.	<i>Rutaceae</i>	Vilaam pazham
94	<i>Lippia nodiflora</i> L.	<i>Verbenaceae</i>	Poduthalai
95	<i>Mangifera indica</i> L.	<i>Anacardiaceae</i>	Maamaram
96	<i>Melia azedarach</i> L.	<i>Meliaceae</i>	Malai veambu
97	<i>Mimosa amara</i> Roxb.	<i>Fabaceae</i>	Oosilmaram
98	<i>Morinda tinctoria</i> Roxb.	<i>Rubiaceae</i>	Nunaa
99	<i>Nymphaea lotus</i> L.	<i>Nymphaeaceae</i>	Allipoo
100	<i>Ocimum basilicum</i> L.	<i>Lamiaceae</i>	Karanthai, Kanjaankorai
101	<i>Ocimum sanctum</i> L.	<i>Lamiaceae</i>	Thulasi
102	<i>Opuntia stricta</i> Haw.	<i>Cactaceae</i>	Sappathikalli
103	<i>Oxalis corniculata</i> L.	<i>Oxalidaceae</i>	Puliaarai
104	<i>Oxystelma esculantum</i> (L.f.) Sm.	<i>Apocynaceae</i>	Oosipaalai
105	<i>Parthenium hysterophorus</i> L.	<i>Asteraceae</i>	Kenathuppoonda
106	<i>Passiflora foetida</i> L.	<i>Passifloraceae</i>	Kurangupazham
107	<i>Pergularia daemia</i> (Forssk.) Chiov.	<i>Asclepiadaceae</i>	Uthaamani, Uthamakannigai
108	<i>Phyllanthus acidus</i> (L.) Skeels.	<i>Phyllanthaceae</i>	Arainellikaai
109	<i>Phyllanthus emblica</i> L.	<i>Phyllanthaceae</i>	Kaatunelli
110	<i>Phyllanthus niruri</i> L.	<i>Phyllanthaceae</i>	Keezhanelli
111	<i>Phyllanthus reticulatus</i> Poir.	<i>Euphorbiaceae</i>	Pallukuchithazhai
112	<i>Physalis minima</i> L.	<i>Solanaceae</i>	Tharmathakkali
113	<i>Psidium guajava</i> L.	<i>Myrtaceae</i>	Koiya
114	<i>Pithecellobium dulce</i> (Roxb.) Benth.	<i>Fabaceae</i>	Kodukapuli, Sulaikaai
115	<i>Plumeria rubra</i> L.	<i>Apocynaceae</i>	Paneerpoo, Kaathuvalipoo

116	<i>Pongamia pinnata</i> (L.) Pierre.	<i>Fabaceae</i>	Pungamaram
117	<i>Prosopis juliflora</i> (Sw.) DC.	<i>Fabaceae</i>	Vealikaathan
118	<i>Punica granatum</i> L.	<i>Lythraceae</i>	Maadulai
119	<i>Randia dumetorum</i> Lam.	<i>Rubiaceae</i>	Aathalankaai
120	<i>Ricinus communis</i> L.	<i>Euphorbiaceae</i>	Aamanakku
121	<i>Saccharum spontaneum</i> L.	<i>Poaceae</i>	Naanal
122	<i>Samanea saman</i> F.Muell.	<i>Fabaceae</i>	Thoongu moonji maram
123	<i>Sansevieria roxburghiana</i> Sch.	<i>Asparagaceae</i>	Marul
124	<i>Sansevieria trifasciata</i> Prain.	<i>Asparagaceae</i>	Kaatumarul
125	<i>Sarcostemma intermedium</i> Decne.	<i>Asclepiadaceae</i>	Kodi kalli
126	<i>Securinega leucopyrus</i> Willd.	<i>Euphorbiaceae</i>	Kaatupila, Pacharisipazham
127	<i>Senna auriculata</i> (L.) Roxb.	<i>Fabaceae</i>	Aavarampoo
128	<i>Sida acuta</i> Burm.f.	<i>Malvaceae</i>	Aruvaamanaipoondu
129	<i>Sida cordifolia</i> L.	<i>Malvaceae</i>	Nilathuthi
130	<i>Smilax zeylanica</i> L.	<i>Smilacaceae</i>	Kaatukodi
131	<i>Solanum trilobatum</i> L.	<i>Solanaceae</i>	Thoothuvalai
132	<i>Solanum xanthocarpum</i> Schrad.	<i>Solanaceae</i>	Kandankathiri
133	<i>Syzygium cumini</i> L.	<i>Myrtaceae</i>	Naaval pazham
134	<i>Tabernaemontana divaricata</i> R.Br. ex Roem. & Schult.	<i>Apocynaceae</i>	Nanthiyavattam
135	<i>Tamarindus indica</i> L.	<i>Fabaceae</i>	Puliyamaram
136	<i>Tectona grandis</i> L.	<i>Liliaceae</i>	Thekkumaram
137	<i>Tephrosia purpurea</i> L.	<i>Fabaceae</i>	Kollukaivelai
138	<i>Tephrosia spinosa</i> (L.) Pers.	<i>Fabaceae</i>	Mugavellai
139	<i>Thespesia populnea</i> (L.) Sol.	<i>Malvaceae</i>	Poovarasu
140	<i>Thevetia peruviana</i> (Pers.) K. Schum.	<i>Apocynaceae</i>	Ponnarali
141	<i>Tinospora cordifolia</i> (Thunb.) Miers.	<i>Menispermaceae</i>	Seenthilkodi
142	<i>Tragia ramosa</i> Torr.	<i>Euphorbiaceae</i>	Ponaikasar
143	<i>Trianthema portulacastrum</i> L.	<i>Aizoaceae</i>	Kuppaikeerai
144	<i>Tribulus lanuginosus</i> L.	<i>Zygophyllaceae</i>	Nerunjil
145	<i>Trichodesma indicus</i> L.	<i>Boraginaceae</i>	Kavizhthumbai
146	<i>Tridax procumbens</i> L.	<i>Asteraceae</i>	Mookuthipoo
147	<i>Unginea indica</i> (Roxb.) Kunt.	<i>Liliaceae</i>	Kaatuvengayam
148	<i>Vernonia cinerea</i> (L.) Less.	<i>Asteraceae</i>	Neichati
149	<i>Wrightia tinctoria</i> (Roxb.) R.Br.	<i>Apocynaceae</i>	Vetpaalai
150	<i>Xanthium strumarium</i> L.	<i>Asteraceae</i>	Seepukaai
151	<i>Ziziphus jujuba</i> Mill.	<i>Rhamnaceae</i>	Ilanthaimaram
152	<i>Ziziphus oenopia</i> (L.) Mill.	<i>Rhamnaceae</i>	Sooraimullu

Table-2. List of crops used for cultivation by farmers in Maruthuvambadi village.

.S.N	Botanical name	Family	Vernacular name
1	<i>Abelmoschus esculentus</i> (L.) Moench.	<i>Malvaceae</i>	Vendaikaai
2	<i>Allium cepa</i> L.	<i>Amaryllidaceae</i>	Vengayam
3	<i>Arachis hypogea</i> L.	<i>Fabaceae</i>	Nilakadalai, Verkadalai, Kadalaikaai
4	<i>Arum colocasia</i> L.	<i>Araceae</i>	Seppangizhangu
5	<i>Basella alba</i> L.	<i>Basellaceae</i>	Pasalai keerai
6	<i>Basella rubra</i> L.	<i>Basellaceae</i>	Kodi pasalai, Sivappu pasalai
7	<i>Benincasa hispida</i> (Thunb.) Cogn.	<i>Cucurbitaceae</i>	Kalyana poosani
8	<i>Brassica juncea</i> L.	<i>Brassicaceae</i>	Kadugu

9	<i>Cajanus indicus</i> . Spreng.	<i>Fabaceae</i>	Thuvarai
10	<i>Capsicum annum</i> L.	<i>Solanaceae</i>	Milakaai
11	<i>Capsicum frutescens</i> L.	<i>Solanaceae</i>	Gundumilagaai
12	<i>Celosia argentea</i> L.	<i>Amaranthaceae</i>	Pannaikerai
13	<i>Celosia cristata</i> L.	<i>Amaranthaceae</i>	Kozhikondai poo
14	<i>Centella asiatica</i> (L.) Urban.	<i>Apiaceae</i>	Vallaraikerai
15	<i>Cephalandra indica</i> Naud.	<i>Cucurbitaceae</i>	Kovaikaai
16	<i>Chrysanthemum coronarium</i> L.	<i>Asteraceae</i>	Saamanthi poo
17	<i>Citrullus lanatus</i> Thunb.	<i>Cucurbitaceae</i>	Tharpoosani
18	<i>Coriandrum sativum</i> L.	<i>Apiaceae</i>	Kothamalli
19	<i>Crossandra infundibuliformis</i> (L.) Nees.	<i>Acanthaceae</i>	Kanakambaram
20	<i>Cucumis sativus</i> L.	<i>Cucurbitaceae</i>	Vellari pazham
21	<i>Curcubita pepo</i> L.	<i>Cucurbitaceae</i>	Poosani
22	<i>Dolichos biflorus</i> L.	<i>Fabaceae</i>	Kollu
23	<i>Eleusine cororana</i> Gaertn.	<i>Gramineae</i>	Kezhvaragu
24	<i>Gisekia pharnaceoides</i> L.	<i>Gisekiaceae</i>	Manalkeerai
25	<i>Gomphrena globosa</i> L.	<i>Amaranthaceae</i>	Vaadamalli
26	<i>Helianthus annuus</i> L.	<i>Asteraceae</i>	Sooriyagaanthi
27	<i>Hibiscus cannabinus</i> L.	<i>Malvaceae</i>	Pulichai keerai
28	<i>Hibiscus surattensis</i> L.	<i>Malvaceae</i>	Kaatupulichai keerai
29	<i>Jasminum sambac</i> (L.) Aiton.	<i>Oleaceae</i>	Malligai
30	<i>Lablab purpureus</i> L.	<i>Fabaceae</i>	Avarai
31	<i>Lagenaria siceraria</i> (Molina) Standl.	<i>Cucurbitaceae</i>	Suraikaai
32	<i>Luffa acutangula</i> (L.) Roxb.	<i>Cucurbitaceae</i>	Peerkankaai
33	<i>Manihot esculenta</i> Crantz.	<i>Euphorbiaceae</i>	Maravalli
34	<i>Marsilea quadrifolia</i> L.	<i>Marsileaceae</i>	Aaraikerai
35	<i>Megathyrsus maximus</i> Jacq.	<i>Poaceae</i>	Theevanappul
36	<i>Momordica charantia</i> L.	<i>Cucurbitaceae</i>	Paagarkaai
37	<i>Moringa oleifera</i> Lam.	<i>Moringaceae</i>	Murungai
38	<i>Murraya koenigii</i> (L.) Sprengel.	<i>Rutaceae</i>	Karuvepilai
39	<i>Musa paradisiaca</i> L.	<i>Musaceae</i>	Vaazhai
40	<i>Nerium oleander</i> L.	<i>Apocynaceae</i>	Arali
41	<i>Oryza sativa</i> L.	<i>Poaceae</i>	Nel
42	<i>Pennisetum glaucum</i> (L.) R.Br.	<i>Poaceae</i>	Kambu
43	<i>Phaseolus mungo</i> L.	<i>Fabaceae</i>	Oulunthu
44	<i>Phaseolus trilobatus</i> L.	<i>Fabaceae</i>	Thattaaan pairu
45	<i>Polianthes tuberosa</i> L.	<i>Asparagaceae</i>	Sampangipoo
46	<i>Portulaca oleracea</i> L.	<i>Portulacaceae</i>	Paruppukeerai
47	<i>Raphanus sativus</i> L.	<i>Brassicaceae</i>	Mullangi
48	<i>Saccharum officinarum</i> L.	<i>Poaceae</i>	Karumbu
49	<i>Sesamum indicum</i> L.	<i>Pedaliaceae</i>	Ellu
50	<i>Solanum melongena</i> L.	<i>Solanaceae</i>	Katharikaai
51	<i>Solanum nigrum</i> L.	<i>Solanaceae</i>	Manathakkali
52	<i>Solanum torvum</i> Sw.	<i>Solanaceae</i>	Sundaikaai
53	<i>Sorghum bicolor</i> (L.) Moench	<i>Poaceae</i>	Solam
54	<i>Trichosanthes cucumerina</i> L.	<i>Cucurbitaceae</i>	Pudalangaai
55	<i>Vigna unguiculata</i> (L.) Walp.	<i>Fabaceae</i>	Kaaramani
56	<i>Vigna radiata</i> (L.) R.Wilczek.	<i>Fabaceae</i>	Pachaippayaru
57	<i>Zea mays</i> L.	<i>Poaceae</i>	Makkasolam

Table-3: List of ornamentals present in Maruthuvambadi village.

S.N	Botanical name	Family	Vernacular name
1	<i>Bougainvillea glabra</i> Choisy.	<i>Nyctaginaceae</i>	Kaakithapoo
2	<i>Impatiens balsamine</i> L.	<i>Balsaminaceae</i>	Baalsampoo
3	<i>Ipomoea quamoclit</i> L.	<i>Convolvulaceae</i>	Mailmaanikkam
4	<i>Ixora coccinea</i> L.	<i>Rubiaceae</i>	Idlypoo
5	<i>Mirabilis jalapa</i> L.	<i>Nyctaginaceae</i>	Anthimalli
6	<i>Pistia stratiotes</i> L.	<i>Araceae</i>	Aagaya thaamarai
7	<i>Polyalthia longifolia</i> Sonn.	<i>Annonaceae</i>	Nettilinkam
8	<i>Portulaca grandiflora</i> Hook.	<i>Portulacaceae</i>	Patturoja
9	<i>Portulaca umbraticola</i> cv. Wildfire Mixed	<i>Portulacaceae</i>	Buttonrose
10	<i>Prunus amygdalus</i> Dulcis.	<i>Rosaceae</i>	Badam
11	<i>Rosa damscena</i> Mill.	<i>Rosaceae</i>	Roja

Table-4: Wild plants present in Maruthuvambadi village.

S.N	Botanical name	Family	Vernacular name
1	<i>Acacia eburnea</i> (L.f.) Willd.	<i>Fabaceae</i>	Karuvelamaram
2	<i>Acacia farnesiana</i> (L.) Willd.	<i>Fabaceae</i>	Peekaruvelamaram
3	<i>Acacia pennata</i> (L.) Willd.	<i>Fabaceae</i>	Kaattusigai
4	<i>Acacia planifrons</i> Wight & Arn.	<i>Fabaceae</i>	Kudaiwelamaram
5	<i>Albizia amara</i> (Roxb.) B. Boivin.	<i>Fabaceae</i>	Oosillai, Thurinjai, Arappu
6	<i>Albizia odoratissima</i> (L.f.) Benth.	<i>Fabaceae</i>	Silai vaagai, Karuvagai
7	<i>Allizzia labbeck</i> (L.) Benth.	<i>Fabaceae</i>	Kaatuvaagai maram
8	<i>Argyreia hookeri</i> C.B.Clarke.	<i>Convolvulaceae</i>	Malaionankodi
9	<i>Aristida setacea</i> Trin.	<i>Poaceae</i>	Poonthudaipam
10	<i>Artocarpus integrifolia</i> Lam.	<i>Moraceae</i>	Palaamaram
11	<i>Asparagus racemosus</i> Willd.	<i>Asparagaceae</i>	Kaatuchedi
12	<i>Atlantia monophylla</i> Roxb.	<i>Rutaceae</i>	Kaattu elumichai
13	<i>Azima tetracantha</i> Lam.	<i>Salvadoraceae</i>	Sangillai, Peankuthi
14	<i>Bambusa bambos</i> (L.) Voss.	<i>Poaceae</i>	Moongil
15	<i>Bassia latifolia</i> Roxb.	<i>Sapotaceae</i>	Iluppaimaram
16	<i>Bauhinia tomentosa</i> (L.) Benth.	<i>Fabaceae</i>	Thiruvaachi
17	<i>Bauhinia variegata</i> (L.) Benth.	<i>Fabaceae</i>	Semmanthaarai
18	<i>Canthium parviflorum</i> Lam.	<i>Rubiaceae</i>	Kaaraikaai, Sirukaarai
19	<i>Capparis brevispina</i> Wight & Arn.	<i>Capparaceae</i>	Aathanthai, Porivilampazham
20	<i>Carmona retusa</i> (Vahl) Masam.	<i>Boraginaceae</i>	Kuruvipazhamsedi, Kurangu vetrilai
21	<i>Cassia fistula</i> L.	<i>Fabaceae</i>	Sarakkondrai
22	<i>Dichrostachys cinerea</i> (L.) Wight & Arn.	<i>Fabaceae</i>	Vedathalam
23	<i>Diospyros ferrea</i> (Willd.) Bakh.	<i>Ebenaceae</i>	Irumbilichedi
24	<i>Lantana camara</i> L.	<i>Verbenaceae</i>	Ounnichedi
25	<i>Madhuca longifolia</i> (J.Konig) J.F.Macbr.	<i>Sapotaceae</i>	Naattuiluppai
26	<i>Phoenix loureirii</i> Kunth.	<i>Arecaceae</i>	Eechamaram
27	<i>Phoenix pusilla</i> Roxb.	<i>Arecaceae</i>	Kaatu eechamaram
28	<i>Pterocarpus marsupium</i> Roxburgh.	<i>Fabaceae</i>	Veangaimaram
29	<i>Spondias pinnata</i> (L.f.) Kurz.	<i>Anacardiaceae</i>	Narimangai
30	<i>Sterculia foetida</i> L.	<i>Malvaceae</i>	Pinarimaram

Conclusion

This survey reveals that plants are still a major source of medicine, food and other purpose for the local communities of most of the portions in our country, because modern healthcare facilities are still insufficient. This simple work may represents a useful and long-lasting document, which can contribute to preserve knowledge on the use of medicinal plants in this village and also stimulate the interest of future generations on traditional healing practices. The information provided in this paper is limited and there is additional scope needed to initiate brief ethnobotanical study. From this survey some important herbals need to be evaluated through phytochemical and pharmacological investigations to discover their potentiality as drugs. This survey is also expected to be useful to botanist, ecologist, crop improvers, plant introducers, students etc. Finally, we concluded that this village was enriched with different kind of plants and furthermore research activities are needed.

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